

**Erosion Characteristics on Surface Texture of Additively
Manufactured AlSi10Mg Alloy in SiO₂ Quartz Added Slurry
Environment**

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Erosion Characteristics on Surface Texture of Additively Manufactured AlSi10Mg Alloy in SiO₂ Quartz Added Slurry Environment

Abstract

Purpose: Additive manufacturing, also known as 3D manufacturing, is the process of manufacturing a part designed in a computer environment using different types of materials such as plastic, ceramic, metal, or composite. Similar to other materials, aluminum alloys are also exposed to various wear types during operation. Production efficiency needs to be aware of its reactions to wearing mechanisms.

Design/ Methodology/ Approach: In this study, quartz sands (SiO₂) assisted with oxide ceramics were used in the slurry erosion test setup and its abrasiveness on the AlSi10Mg aluminum alloy material produced by the 3D printer as Selective Laser Melting (SLM) technology was investigated. Quartz was sieved with an average particle size of 302.5 μm and a slurry environment containing 5%, 10%, and 15% quartz by weight was prepared. The experiments were carried out at the velocity of 1.88 m/s (250 rpm), 3.76 m/s (500 rpm), and 5.64 m/s (750 rpm) and the impact angles 15°, 45°, and 75°.

Findings: With these experimental studies, it has been determined that the abrasiveness of quartz sand prepared in certain particle sizes is directly related to the particle concentration and particle speed and that the wear increases with the increase of the concentration and rotational speed. Also, the variation of weight loss and surface roughness of the alloy was investigated after different wear conditions. Surface roughness values at 750 rpm speed, 10% concentration, and 75° impingement angle are 0.32 μm and 0.38 μm for 0° and 90° samples, respectively, with a difference of approximately 18%. Moreover, concerning a sample produced at 0°, the weight loss at 250 rpm at 10% concentration and 45° particle impact angle is 32.8 mg, while the weight loss at 500 rpm 44.4 mg, and weight loss at 750 rpm is 104 mg. Besides, the morphological structures of eroded surfaces were examined using SEM (Scanning Electron Microscope) to understand the wear mechanisms.

Keywords: Additive manufacturing, AlSi10Mg, Quartz sand, Slurry erosion, Surface roughness.

Paper type- Research paper

1. Introduction

According to the ASTM (American Society for Testing and Materials) standard F2792-1, additive manufacturing is the process of combining materials, often in layers on top of each other, to make objects from 3D model data, as opposed to subtractive manufacturing methodologies such as traditional machining (Du *et al.*, 2019; Szymczyk *et al.*, 2020). Production technologies are known as three-dimensional (3D) manufacturing or additive manufacturing have a wide range of uses. Therefore, many companies and research institutions commonly use additive manufacturing methods instead of traditional methods (Łyczkowska *et al.*, 2014; Singla *et al.*, 2021). Due to the advantages, additive manufacturing has widespread use that ensures the rapid development of the filament, materials, and techniques (Lifton *et al.*, 2021). Additive manufacturing methods are opposite of conventional machining methods. In machining, the chips are removed from the base material and a product of the desired shape and size is obtained, while in additive manufacturing, the parts are combined in layers (Ramoni *et al.*, 2021; Waqar, Guo, *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, the use of materials in additive manufacturing is less than traditional machining (Rautio *et al.*, 2020; Zhang *et al.*, 2021). In additive manufacturing methods, materials such as metal, ceramic, plastic, composite can be used, as well as specific production materials (Gupta *et al.*, 2020; Waqar *et al.*, 2020). In addition to its wide range of materials, its use is increasing day by day as it enables the production of parts with very complex geometries with minimum material loss (Waqar, Sun, *et al.*, 2021). Many materials such as ABS (Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene), plastic, polyamide (nylon), glass-filled polyamide, stereolithography materials (epoxy resins), silver, titanium, steel, aluminum, wax, photopolymers, and polycarbonate can be used as consumables materials in 3D printers (Damodaran *et al.*, 2021; Le *et al.*, 2017). It enables green production as it is easier to use environmentally friendly and ecologically friendly materials in additive manufacturing (Kurzynowski *et al.*, 2020). The concept of "green production", which is becoming increasingly important today, is important for a more livable future. Green production is the renewal of production steps and the use of environmentally friendly methods and materials in production. The use of less natural resources by the workforce, less waste and pollution, and the recycling of products can be considered within the scope of green production (Farooque *et al.*, 2019; Junjun *et al.*, 2018). Aluminum is the most

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3 abundant element in the world after silicon and oxygen. About 8% of the elements in the
4 earth's crust are aluminum and its compounds. Aluminum and its alloys, due to its many
5 advantages such as being abundant in nature, easy to obtain, low weight, suitable
6 mechanical properties (having a high strength/weight ratio) (Manjunath Patel *et al.*,
7 2020), high thermal and electrical conductivity, resistance to odor and chemicals,
8 recyclability (Vargel, 2020). Various aluminum metal powder mixtures such as AlSi10Mg
9 (Xu *et al.*, 2021), AlSi7Mg (Wang *et al.*, 2019) and AlSi12 (Xi *et al.*, 2018) are used in metal
10 additive manufacturing technologies depending on the desired product properties
11 (Aboulkhair *et al.*, 2017, 2019). SLM (selective laser melting) production technique used
12 in this study is similar to SLS (selective laser sintering) and the only difference is that the
13 powder is melted instead of sintering with this method (Tawfik *et al.*, 2019; Zhang, Liu, *et*
14 *al.*, 2018). With the SLM method, complex 3D models can be produced in layers within a
15 few hours (Olakanmi, 2013; Olakanmi *et al.*, 2015). Cobalt-chrome, stainless steels,
16 Inconel, titanium, and aluminum powders can be used as raw materials. It is a great
17 technology for specific productions. Regardless of the method used, every material must
18 have a certain wear resistance (Chawla and Shen, 2001). Wear is a situation that directly
19 affects the life of the equipment in the plants. There are many types of wear and one of
20 the most common problems is an erosive wear (Bansal *et al.*, 2020; Fouad *et al.*, 2011;
21 Venter *et al.*, 2020). About erosive wear, there are also many different wear types
22 (Raadnui, 2021; Saleh *et al.*, 2021; Verma, 2020). Slurry erosive wear is one of these wear
23 types and occurs especially in liquid environments containing a certain quantity of solid
24 particles (Heshmat and Abdelrhman, 2021; Kumar *et al.*, 2020). The facilities where this
25 type of wear is most common are the facilities where quartz sand (Chen *et al.*, 2020;
26 Matikainen *et al.*, 2019), which is a raw material for glass and ceramic, is occurred. SiO₂
27 is displayed when talked about glaze chemistry in pottery. An oxide contributed by many
28 ceramic materials such as all clays, feldspars and frits. Quartz or silica powder is almost
29 100% SiO₂. However, quartz sand of SiO₂ is completely different from feldspar SiO₂. In
30 the latter, it chemically binds to Al₂O₃ and also other oxide ceramics. These quartz sands
31 are pumped to manufacturing plants with high amounts of water by using pumps. The
32 equipment on the line is exposed to slurry erosive wear and worn out in a short time
33 (Clark and Llewellyn, 2001; Ojala *et al.*, 2016). Some current studies on AlSi10Mg alloy
34 produced with SLM technology and also combined with slurry wear type are summarized
35 below and no studies on slurry wear with oxide ceramic assisted SiO₂ quartz sands have
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3 been found. Li et al. investigated the building orientation on the tensile properties of
4 additively manufactured AlSi10Mg alloy produced with SLM (Li *et al.*, 2021). Atzeni et al.
5 examined the applicability of the abrasive fluidized bed (AFB) method as a finishing
6 process on AlSi10Mg alloyed surfaces produced by direct metal laser sintering (DMLS)
7 (Atzeni *et al.*, 2016). Brandl et al. investigated the microstructure, high cycle fatigue (HCF),
8 and breakage behavior of AlSi10Mg samples produced and processed by the selective
9 laser melting (SLM) method. (Brandl *et al.*, 2012). Hadadzadeh et al. investigated the effect
10 of the building orientation for AlSi10Mg alloy produced by direct metal laser sintering
11 (DMLS) on the columnar to coaxial transition (CET) behavior. (Hadadzadeh, Amirkhiz, Li,
12 *et al.*, 2018). Nurel et al. applied Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB-PHC) tests to
13 AlSi10Mg alloy samples produced by the SLM method to investigate their dynamic
14 properties. (Nurel *et al.*, 2018). There are much more studies in the literature about
15 AlSi10Mg alloy produced with SLM as shown in Table 1. Most of these studies are about
16 the determination of mechanical properties, fatigue properties, dynamic behaviors and
17 corrosion types (Beevers *et al.*, 2018; Cabrini *et al.*, 2016; Hadadzadeh, Amirkhiz, Odeshi,
18 *et al.*, 2018; Maconachie *et al.*, 2020; Zhang, Zhu, *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, about the slurry
19 wear process, Patel et al. (Patel *et al.*, 2018) studied on microstructural analysis and wear
20 behaviour after slurry erosion tests for A2024- SiC-ZrSiO₄ metal matrix composites. The
21 author indicated that the weight loss increased with increasing rotational speed and
22 supported this situation with microstructural changes. Fals et al. (Fals *et al.*, 2020)
23 examined the slurry wear resistance of AISI 1020 steel which is thermally sprayed
24 deposited with Nb₂O₅ and Nb₂O₅+WC₁₂Co coating. The researchers verified that this
25 specific coating condition increases the slurry wear resistance of the mentioned steel.
26 There are lots of study about slurry wear tests, however, there is no study in the literature
27 about the quartz sand (SiO₂) assisted slurry-erosive wear of AlSi10Mg alloy produced
28 with AM by using SLM technology. This study is needed to fill this gap in the literature and
29 to examine the erosive wear capability of this current material in different environments.
30 The novelty of the study is the use of SiO₂ quartz sands assisted by oxide ceramics in
31 different concentrations for the slurry erosion test setup and the investigations on erosive
32 wear resistance of AlSi10Mg alloy manufactured by AM.
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57 Table 1. Literature studies about SLMed AlSi10Mg

Material and Building Directions	Aim of the study	Authors
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Single directional of pure- AlSi10Mg and nano additive AlSi10Mg	Investigation of the mechanical properties	(Wang and Shi, 2020)
Single directional of carbon- AlSi10Mg	Assessment of the mechanical and electrical properties	(Zhao <i>et al.</i> , 2016)
Three directional of SLMed AlSi10Mg	Evaluation of the mechanical and sliding wear properties	(Kan <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
Single directional of untreated- AlSi10Mg and T6 heat treated- AlSi10Mg	Investigation of the hardness, tribological and corrosion properties	(Wei <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
Four directional of SLMed AlSi10Mg	Study of the fatigue and crack behaviour	(Xu <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
Two directional of SLMed AlSi10Mg	Assessment of the microstructure and void dependence of tensile properties	(Ben <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Single directional of SLMed AlSi10Mg	Investigation of the mechanical properties in three different melting mode transition	(Wu <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
Two directional of SLMed AlSi10Mg	Effect of T6 treatment sliding against ceramic and steel	(Kan <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
Single directional of SLMed AlSi10Mg	Plasma electrolytic oxidation treatment on corrosion and sliding wear performances	(Liu <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
Single directional of SLMed AlSi10Mg	Melt spreading behavior, microstructure evolution and wear resistance	

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Preparation of abrasive particles and slurry

The oxide ceramics assisted quartz sands were used as the abrasive material. The measurement of particle size distribution is necessary to determine the percentage of particles in the sample of different size ranges. A dry sieve analysis can be used to determine the particle size distribution. Representing the abrasive sample, a sample is taken from the sample and sifted through a series of sieves. Standard quantity percentages are calculated by weighing the samples held in each sieve (More *et al.*, 2014). In this study, the dry sieve method was applied as clearly stated in the literature. Before weighing, the sample was carefully dried and dehumidified. Percentage distributions of particle sizes were obtained and it was determined that approximately 60% of them were between 180 μm and 425 μm (Table 2). Abrasive particles with an average particle size of 302.5 μm were prepared by sieving the abrasive in sieves with 425 μm and 180 μm openings, respectively. The chemical composition obtained in the XRF (X-Ray Emission Spectroscopy) device of ARL Advant in Table 3 and the SEM images before and after the sieving process in Figure 1 are given. As seen in the SEM image, the abrasive particles used have sharp edges and irregular geometry.

Table 2. Dimensional distribution results according to the sieving process performed following ASTM E 11:82 standard.

Sieve Opening (μm)	Weight (gr)	Differential (%)	Cumulative Under the Sieve (%)
+600	0.25	0.22	100.00
-600 +500	3.21	2.87	99.78
-500 +425	8.16	7.29	96.91
-425 +355	12.14	10.84	89.63
-355 +180	55.35	49.42	78.79
-180 +150	12.12	10.82	29.37
-150 +106	13.43	11.99	18.54
-106	7.34	6.55	6.55
Total	112.00	100.00	-

Table 3. Chemical composition of oxide ceramic assisted quartz sand sample

	SiO ₂	CaO	Al ₂ O ₃	MgO	Fe ₂ O ₂	K ₂ O	TiO ₂	Other
Quantity (wt %)	98.3	0	0.74	0.04	0.0065	0.27	0.12	0.5235

Figure 1. SEM image of quartz sample a) before sieving process b) after sieving process

2.2. Fabrication of samples

In this study, AlSi10Mg test specimens were produced at 0° and 90° building orientations by using a Concept Laser branded Mlab 200R 3D metal printer performed with Selective Laser Melting (SLM) technique by Form Additive Corporation (Figure 2). AlSi10Mg powder (30 μm size) mixture with code "EOS art-no 9011-0024" was used in the

production and chemical composition of the powders is shown in Table 4. No heat treatment has been applied to the test samples. Finally, the sanding process was performed to the additively manufacture AlSi10Mg alloys. The optical microscope images of the samples with 0° and 90° building orientations are given in Figure 3. The etching process before taking the optical images, the samples were etched by the solution of 190 mL H₂O + 5 mL HNO₃ + 3 mL HCl + 2mL HF with a duration of 60 sec.

Figure 2. AlSi10Mg alloy, a) printer, b) 0° building orientations, c) 90° building orientations

Figure 3. Optical microscope images of the samples with building direction of, a) 0°, b) 90°

Table 4. The chemical composition of the AlSi10Mg powders.

Si (9.0 - 11.0 wt-%)	Fe (0.55 wt-%)	Cu (0.05 wt-%)
Mn (0.45 wt-%)	Mg (0.2 - 0.45 wt-%)	Ni (0.05 wt-%)
Zn (0.10 wt-%)	Pb (0.05 wt-%)	Sn (0.05 wt-%)
Ti (0.15 wt-%)	Porosity (0,15 wt-%)	Al (Balanced)

Before starting the slurry erosion test, the surfaces were sanded with 1200 grit silicon carbide emery paper. With this process, specimens have similar surface roughness values were tried to be prepared. At the end of the sanding, it is aimed to compare the final conditions of the surfaces of the materials exposed to slurry erosion. The surface images of both specimens after the sanding process are given in Figure 4. Besides, the hardness and roughness values of the surface of the specimens are given in Table 5.

Figure 4. Surface images of specimens after sanding a) 0°, b) 90°

Table 5. Hardness and roughness values of the surface of the specimens

Building direction of the Specimens	0°	90°
Hardness [HV-100kgf]	132	130
Ra [μm]	0.08	0.082

2.3. Slurry erosion experiments

Slurry erosion is generally defined as the removal of material from contact surfaces by solid particles in the liquid environment. This environment is not only liquid but also gas fluid. The experimental setup was designed to test the parameters affecting slurry erosion (Figure 5). It is on the same principle as the experimental setup designed by (More *et al.*, 2014). There are a total of six plates in the chamber, which have an inner diameter of 240 mm and a volume of 10 lt. At the bottom of the chamber, there is a four-bladed mixing propeller as seen in Figure 5a. This mixer is driven by an AC motor with 1.1 kW power, using a belt-pulley mechanism. Samples are connected to the system with the help of sample holders. The sample holders are attached to the arm holder using the arms as seen in Figure 5.b, and the handle holder to the shaft. This shaft is rotated around its axis using a belt-pulley mechanism with another AC motor with 1.1 kW power. Due to the rotational movement around this axis and the adjustable position of the sample holders, the contact

of the quartz particles with the sample can be at different impact angles. Sample holders, arms, and cylindrical arm holders to which the arms are connected are made of stainless steel material for long life. In the wear measurements, the erosion occurring in these sample holders was not taken into consideration, and the same sample holders were used in many tests. The rotation radius (R) of the holders attached to the sample arms is 72 mm in Figure 5c. Samples are 30 x 5 x 6 mm in size. The surface size exposed to erosion is 30 x 5 mm as seen in Figure 5d.

Figure 5. Test Rig, a) assembly, b) tank, c) specimen holders, d) specimen, e) whole test setup, f) slurry erosive wear mechanism

Before experiments, the samples were cleaned with tap water, dried by using a hairdryer, and weighed with a scale of 0.1 mg sensitivity. The same cleaning process was repeated after each experiment. After the samples were placed on the sample holder, they were fixed with the help of fixing bolts, not by adhesion material, contrary to the previous experiments. Since no adhesives were used, no chemicals were required to clean the samples for weighing after the test. The duration of the experiments was limited to one hour to prevent the reduction of the abrasive effect caused by the change in articulate

sizes and the sharp edge changing on the abrasive surfaces. To obtain good results, the same experiment was repeated five times and the wear values were averaged. The contact area is 1.5 cm² (30 x 5 mm) for each sample. After each test, the used quartz was evacuated from the system and the new quartz that had been prepared previously was included in the system. Again, after each test, the inner surfaces of the sample holders were cleaned with pressurized water to prevent any residue. (Lindsley and Marder, 1999) considered particle velocity as a critical test meter in their study and different velocities were determined as target material. They stated that the effects on them are very easily discernible and that the increase in erosive wear is obtained by increasing the speed. Besides, Desale et al. (Desale *et al.*, 2008) concluded that besides velocity and particle size, the ambient solid concentration is also an effective parameter on the erosive wear value. In this study, to examine these parameters, 3 different concentration values of sludge were prepared, three different rotation speed values, and 3 different impact angle values were used (Table 6). The rotational speed given in Table 7, corresponding to the velocity values of 1.88 m/s, 3.76 m/s, and 5.64 m/s respectively (Table 6), have been selected as 250 500 and 750 rpm. Mixer speed was kept constant as 600 rpm in the experiments. The direction of rotation of the sample and the direction of rotation of the mixer are arranged in different directions. The mixing propeller, which is used to prevent the quartz particles from settling to the bottom of the chamber, has been ensured that the mixture is uniform. In addition, the propeller blade positions are designed to move the quartz movements from the center to the chamber wall and from there upwards. During the experiment, six plates on the chamber walls prevented the quartz particles from making circular movements in the direction of sample rotation. In the experiments, besides the speed, the solid concentration was chosen as 5%, 10% and 15% at three different values. In addition, three different values were used as the impact angle as 15 °, 45 ° and 75 °. Finally, Mahr Perthometer profilometer was used for the measurement of average surface roughness values which was obtained as third time and then averaged.

Table 6. Relationship between velocity and rotational speed

Velocity [m/s]		Rotational Speed [rpm]
1,88	$n = \frac{60V}{2\pi R} [rpm]$	250
3,76		500
5,64		750

Table 7. Experimental Design

	Factor	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
A	Rotational speed (rpm)	250	500	750
B	Impact angle (°)	15	45	75
C	Concentration (%)	5	10	15

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Weight loss evaluation

As a result of the experiments performed at different abrasive concentrations, impact angles, and speeds, the weight loss of the samples was measured. Comparisons were made on weight loss since there was no change in self-weight. Within the scope of three different tests carried out for each test condition, the wear values of a total of six samples were averaged. When the wear values are examined, it is seen that the wear values increase with the increase in the speed for all concentration and impact angle values. Among the parameters examined, the most effective parameter value is the rotational speed value and it is much more effective on weight loss compared to the impact angle and concentration parameters. (Razzaque *et al.*, 2016).

Figure 6. Weight loss under different wear conditions for 0° samples

Figure 7. 3D-Weight loss graph under interactions of process parameters for 0° samples

Figure 8. Weight loss under different wear conditions for 90° samples

Figure 9. 3D-Weight loss graph under interactions of process parameters for 90° samples

When Figures 6 and 8 are evaluated, concerning a sample produced at 0°, the weight loss at 250 rpm at 10% concentration and 45° particle impact angle is 32.8 mg, while the weight loss at 500 rpm 44.4 mg, and weight loss at 750 rpm is 104 mg. The average increases of the weight loss are 35% and 235% when the revolution speed value increases from 250 to 500 rpm and 500 rpm to 750 rpm, respectively. The increase in the amount of wear that occurs with the increase in the speed can be interpreted as the kinetic energies gained by the particles play a more effective role at high speeds. Figures 7 and 9 show that the rotational speed is the most important factor affecting weight loss of AlSi10Mg under a slurry erosive wear environment. As interpreted by Das et al. (Das *et al.*, 2006) and Mao et al. (Mao *et al.*, 2018), the wear rate in parallel with weight loss increases by increasing rotational speed. A variation of abrasive wear, erosive wear, and corrosive wear was used to describe why the behavior happened. From this point of view, it is important to select the appropriate speed in slurry pipelines by taking into account the effective role the speed plays in weight loss after a certain point. When Fig.8 is evaluated, the weight loss increased with increasing concentration values. The increase in weight loss of the specimens is mostly due to an increase in the concentration of abrasive particles in the slurry, which increases the chances of abrasive particles impinging on the specimen, resulting in increased corrosion and material removal from the surface (Rawat *et al.*, 2017; Sanman and Sreenivas Rao, 2018). Considering the

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3 variation between impact angles at the same speed and the same concentration values,
4 increasing the particle impact angle from 45 ° to 75 ° at 250 rpm and 5% concentration
5 for a sample produced at 0 °, while the weight loss decreases by 552%, while the same
6 concentration at 750 rpm. The weight loss is reduced by 126% by increasing the particle
7 impact angle from 45 ° to 75 ° at rpm. From this, it can be concluded that the effect of the
8 change in speed is more than the effect of the change in the angle of impact. Even at low
9 speeds, the effect of the change in the impact angle occurs more than the effect of the angle
10 change at high speeds. At narrow impact angles, wear is mainly due to the speed of the
11 particle parallel to the target surface and is similar to machining done by a machine during
12 metal cutting (Finnie and McFadden, 1978). Impact energy and particle shape can play an
13 important role at acute angles because the angular particle shape can have a series of
14 cutting edges that can penetrate deep into the surface with higher impact energy (Shitole
15 *et al.*, 2015). The material loss value at 15 ° impact angle is highest at 45 ° strike angle and
16 decreases as the strike angle increases towards the normal strike angle (Patil *et al.*, 2011).
17 For all speed and concentration values related to the impact angles, it can be evaluated
18 that the wear values are at 75 °, 15 °, and 45 ° impact angles, respectively, from small to
19 large. For example, for a sample produced with 90 °, the values at 15 °, 45 ° and 75 ° for
20 500 rpm and 15% concentration value are 56mg, 62mg, and 43mg respectively. As can be
21 seen, the least abrasion occurred at 75 ° and the most abrasion at 45 °.

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With this study, it has been revealed that there are wear differences between the samples
manufactured with a 3D printer in 0 ° and 90 ° directions. In almost all of the data
obtained, especially at high speeds, with a few exceptions such as 500rpm speed, 5%
concentration, and 45 ° impact angle, commonly more wear appeared for the 90 ° samples.
For example, wear values for 500 rpm, 10% concentration, and 45 ° angle value for 0° and
90° directional samples are 32.7mg and 38mg, respectively. The more measured wear
values in parts manufactured with 90 ° are thought to be due to the production method.
It is recommended to produce 3D materials to be used in slurry pipelines at 0 ° building
direction.

3.2. Surface roughness analysis

In the study, the most important criteria for slurry erosive wear were evaluated according
to wear parameters of average surface roughness (Ra) based on the related studies like
Xiulin *et al.* (Ji *et al.*, 2012) and Goyal *et al.* (Goyal *et al.*, 2012). With the increase in the

speed and concentration, a significant increase in surface roughness occurred. This increase can be explained by the increase in the number of particles hitting the wear surface.

Figure 10. Surface roughness under different wear conditions for 0° samples

Figure 11. 3D-surface roughness graph under interactions of process parameters for 0° samples

Figure 12. Surface roughness under different wear conditions for 90° samples

Figure 13. 3D-surface roughness graph under interactions of process parameters for 90° samples

It can be seen from Figure 10, the surface roughness values are 0.22 µm, 0.23 µm, and 0.24 µm for the 250 rpm for 0° sample and 5%, 10%, and 15% concentration values for the 15° impact angle, respectively. The increase in surface roughness by increase of quartz

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3 concentration can be attributed to the high hardness of SiO₂ quartz particles. As
4 interpreted by Raadnui (Raadnui, 2021), this property affects the erosive wear of the
5 propeller surface by different mechanisms. SiO₂ erosive particles having higher fracture
6 toughness generally tend to being as smaller particles and cause poor surface quality.
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8 Figures 11 and 13 show that the impact angle is the most important factor affecting the
9 surface roughness of AlSi10Mg under a slurry erosive wear environment. As can be seen
10 from Figures 10 and 12, the surface roughness value has the highest value at the highest
11 concentration value. An increase in particle concentration in a multiphase flow system
12 enhances surface damage through cutting action, scratching, and material removal
13 (Elemuren *et al.*, 2019). Since the 75 ° impact angle is close to the 90 ° impact angle
14 expressed as the normal impact angle in the literature, deformation wear plays a more
15 effective role than the cutting wear. This explains the increase in surface roughness with
16 increasing angle of impact (Desale *et al.*, 2006). For example, for 750 rpm speed and 15%
17 concentration, the values at 15 °, 45 °, and 75 ° particle impact angles are 0.22 μm, 0.34
18 μm, and 0.37 μm respectively. As can be seen, the highest surface roughness value was
19 obtained at a particle impact angle of 75 °. The wear mechanism in the SiO₂ quartz added
20 slurry erosive wear tends to be identical to the surface wear mechanisms of micro
21 plowing and micro-cutting. The hard SiO₂ quartz phase distribution tends to have a strong
22 influence on the wear volume in the slurry test.
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3.3. Worn surface analysis

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40 The effect of the particle impact angle on the weight loss occurring in the material has also
41 been proved by SEM images taken from the worn surfaces (Figure 14). The fact that the
42 sanding marks are still present at 15 degrees indicates that there will be less deviation
43 from the initial roughness value than other angles. By analyzing the wear difference in 0
44 and 90° building orientation, it is understood from the optical image (Figure 14) that the
45 amounts of grain boundaries have changed. Due to the increase in the number of
46 embedded particles due to the grain boundary at 0°, this increase may cause less weight
47 loss than the 90° sample due to the loss of the main material, although it brings additional
48 weight to the sample. Although wear losses are normally close, embedded particle
49 additional weights may cause the difference to be overestimated.
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Figure 14. Surface images after slurry erosion with building direction of, a) 0°, b) 90°

Materials processed in SLM can experience very high cooling rates of $10^6 - 10^8$ K/s, which can profoundly affect the behavior of the SLMed alloy. At these cooling rates, diffusion-driven solid-state phase transformation can be completely suppressed. In addition, the formation of supersaturated solutions, non-equilibrium phases and ultrafine microstructures with very little elemental separations are possible (Yazdian *et al.*, 2010). Figure 14a and 14b show the optical images in the building directions of 0° and 90°, respectively. The geometry of the melt pool appeared crescent and irregular in shape due to the application of alternative hatching patterns. The structures of Al and Si cells in the matrix and grain boundary region, respectively, were found to be continuous in the entire melt pool region except the adjacent Heat Affected Zone (HAZ)s due to the overdispersion of Si particles near the melt pool boundary. This reveals Si morphology and appearances as idiomorphic crystals (Thijs *et al.*, 2013). The unstable SLM process presents a higher solidification rate, which further changes the phase formation, the limit of solid solubility. Rapid solidification promotes segregation of Si particles at the grain boundary where they combine with other Si particles resulting in a reduction in the total Si number. At the same time, the solid solubility of Si in Al increases, resulting in a supersaturated solution. Solubility can be further increased with varying processing parameters, promoting higher cooling rates (Lam *et al.*, 2015; Rao *et al.*, 2016).

Figure 15. Surface roughness variations based on impact angle, a) 15°, b) 45° and c) 75°.

Figure 15a shows the worn surface with the lowest impact angle. This surface appears to be less worn than other surfaces as expected. Besides, when the impact angle increases, in addition to surface deformations, surface cracks caused by SiO_2 particles are also noticed. On the other hand, the excess of the roughness values on the surfaces of the material samples produced with 90° can be explained by the excess weight loss. As can be seen from Figures 10 and 12, surface roughness values at 750 rpm speed, 10% concentration, and 75° impingement angle are $0.32\mu\text{m}$ and $0.38\mu\text{m}$ for 0° and 90° samples, respectively, with a difference of approximately 18%. Besides, the SEM images obtained for 0° and 90° samples prove that the 90° sample is worn more and the surface roughness is more than the 0° sample (Figure.16).

Figure 16. Worn surfaces for the rotational speed of 750 rpm, impact angle of 75° and the concentration of 15% with building direction of, a) 0° , b) 90° .

As can be seen from Figure 16, the sample with 0° building direction was a smooth surface, but surface microcracks were encountered. However, in the sample with 90° building direction, deep wear marks and surface microcracks are seen. This situation shows that the sample with a building direction of 90° cannot be able to withstand the powder building direction. The image of SiO_2 erodent particles seen in Figure 16 after slurry erosion tests are given in Figure 17 at high magnification. Here, SiO_2 particles of all sizes are encountered as expected. Finally, EDS analysis was performed on the worn image taken from a sample (Figure 18).

Figure 17. SEM image of quartz samples after slurry erosive test

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Figure 18. EDS analysis of worn surfaces of AlSi10Mg alloy with SiO₂ erodent particles

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3 Here, zones 1 and 3 denote the AlSi10Mg alloy, and zones 2 and 4 denote SiO₂ abrasive
4 particles, as can be understood from their Si and O ratios. This showed that the various
5 degrees of abrasion were observed on a different region of worn surfaces of AlSi10Mg
6 alloy. As the abrasive aspect from SiO₂ quartz is emphasized in the outer strip, more
7 attention should be paid to decrease the risk of wear. Especially the point 2 (SiO₂ erodent
8 particle) verified itself to be an abrasive particle. General results of EDX performed on
9 slurry erosion test samples show that the columnar composition is the same as the
10 composition of the initial components (AlSi10Mg and SiO₂). There are no steps and there
11 is a clear difference from what the configuration is described.
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20 4. Conclusions

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22 This study aims to evaluate the effects of the rotational speed, impact angle, and SiO₂
23 concentrations on the weight loss and surface roughness during the slurry - erosive wear
24 tests on AlSi10Mg alloy produced by additive manufacturing. Some remarkable results
25 are summarized below.
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- 29 • It is seen that the wear values increase with the increase in the rotational speed
30 for all concentration and impact angle values.
- 31 • It is important to select the appropriate speed in slurry pipelines, taking into
32 account the effective role the speed plays in weight loss after a certain point.
- 33 • The effect of the change in speed is more than the effect of the change in the angle
34 of impact. Even at low speeds, the effect of the change in angle of impact occurs
35 more than the effect of the angle change at high speeds. At narrow impact angles,
36 wear is mainly due to the speed of the particle parallel to the target surface and is
37 similar to machining during metal cutting.
- 38 • The least erosive wear (weight loss) occurred at 75 °, while the most occurred at
39 45 °.
- 40 • With the increase in the rotational speed and concentration, a significant increase
41 in surface roughness occurred.
- 42 • Since the 75 ° impact angle is close to the 90 ° impact angle expressed as the normal
43 impact angle in the literature, deformation wear plays a more effective role than
44 the cutting wear.
- 45 • When the impact angle increases, in addition to surface deformations, surface
46 cracks caused by oxide ceramics assisted SiO₂ particles are also seen.
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- The sample of 90° building direction is worn more and the surface roughness is more than the sample produced at 0° building direction.
- Optimization and modelling on tribological studies can be performed for the future research about additively manufactured AlSi10Mg alloy.

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